

Paper 10

STUDY OF KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT POLICIES AND KNOWLEDGE SHARING IN SOFTWARE INDUSTRIES

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Abstract:

Background of the Study:

Knowledge Management (KM) is defined as those processes, tools and infrastructures by which an organization continuously improves, maintains and exploits all those elements of its knowledge base which the organization believes are relevant to achieving its goals.

Knowledge Management helps to improve the overall organizational performance. Active and dynamic implementation and management of knowledge are the two critical ways of enabling organizational performance enhancements, problem solving and decision making (Liebowitz, 1999).

Knowledge is often defined as a “justified personal belief.” There are much taxonomy that specify various kinds of knowledge. The most fundamental distinction is between “tacit” and “explicit” knowledge. (King, 2009)

Objective – This research attempts to study the importance of knowledge management policies and knowledge sharing in software industries.

Design/methodology/approach –The questionnaire on the two dimensions namely Knowledge Management policies and knowledge sharing of knowledge management (having 7 and 9 questions respectively) was prepared and distributed in Google Forms to the employees of different software companies. 141 employees from different software industries were responded to the questionnaire. The questionnaire had 13 a priori items on a Likert 5-point scale (5-strongly agree and 1-Strongly disagree).

This study tests only one main hypothesis (the role of knowledge management policies and knowledge sharing in effectiveness of knowledge management).

Total responses for each category is tabulated, analyzed and graph was prepared to show the importance of each of the factors in the knowledge management

Results and Discussions: Total of 141 responses were collected from different employees by distribution of questionnaire..

Out of 141 responses 77% of the employees have accepted that they have Knowledge Management policies in their organizations and 74% accepted that they have knowledge sharing methods in their organizations.

Conclusions:

The knowledge management policies and knowledge sharing methods are proved to be two important dimensions of knowledge management adopted in software industries.

Keywords: Knowledge Management, Knowledge Management policies and knowledge sharing

References:

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2. William R. King, (ed) 2009, Knowledge Management and Organizational Learning, Volume 4